

Communication and Dissemination plan

Deliverable 7.1
Andreas Villareal and Anya Gregory,
ARCTIK
April 2023

IMPETUS
4CHANGE
TO CHANGE

Funded by the
European Union

Version 1
 April 2023

Deliverable 7.1: Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan

Lead by Arctik

Anya Gregory (Arctik), Andreas Villareal (Arctik), Mathew Reeve (NORSE)

Dissemination level of document

Public

Abstract

This document summarises the plan and specific actions to be taken by the WP7 team to achieve the communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives of the project. The plan will be used as a reference point throughout the project to ensure that all activities create a high level of impact, are holistically taking into consideration the activities of other work packages and come together cohesively to create a streamlined approach to external communication.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors	Description
V1	28.04.2023	Anya Gregory (Arctik), Andreas Villareal (Arctik), Mathew Reeve (NORSE) Error! Reference source not found.	First full draft of strategy
V2			
V3			

Table of contents

1.	<u>Introduction</u>	5
1.1	Communication, dissemination, and exploitation	6
1.1.1	Communication	6
	Communication goals	7
1.1.2	Dissemination	7
	Dissemination goals	8
1.1.3	Exploitation	8
	Exploitation goals	8
2.	<u>Overarching objectives</u>	9
2.1	Short term objectives	9
2.2	Long-term objectives	10
3.	<u>Target audiences and messages</u>	11
3.1	Main target audiences	11
3.2	Sample messages per audience	11
4.	<u>Content strategy – Methodology</u>	14
4.1	Raising awareness and ‘the Marketing Funnel’	14
4.2	Engagement triangle	16
5.	<u>Project branding</u>	17
5.1	Visual identity and templates	17
5.2	Flyer	17
6.	<u>Tools and channels</u>	18
6.1	Owned tools and channels	18
	6.1.1 Project website	18
	6.1.2 Social media	18

6.1.3 Newsletter	20
<u>7. Making I4C actionable – Dissemination and engagement</u>	21
7.1 Promoting accessibility	21
7.1.1 Videos	21
7.2 Multipliers	21
7.2.1 Mapping multipliers and newsletters	22
7.2.2 Toolkit	22
7.2.3 Media engagement	22
7.3 Dissemination	23
7.2.1 Policy briefs	23
5.2.5 Scientific publications and Zenodo	23
<u>8. Events</u>	23
8.1 Climate Adaptalabs	23
8.2 Roadshow	24
8.3 External events	24
8.3.1 Mapping external events	25
<u>9. Monitoring and evaluation</u>	25
9.1 Bi-monthly internal communication	25
9.2 Communication/dissemination tracker	25
9.3 Communication KPIs	25
9.3 Challenges and opportunities	26
9.4 List of deliverables	27
<u>10. Appendix</u>	28

1. Introduction

- This document outlines the Impetus 4 Change (I4C) communication and dissemination strategy, which aims to effectively guide communication and dissemination activities throughout the project's duration. The strategy will also inform the exploitation strategy to be developed later in the project, contributing to the project's potential impact and successful implementation.
- The primary objectives of the communication strategy are to increase awareness and understanding of the project objectives, provide accessible information and guidance on climate information and services, enhance the quality of near-term climate information and services, foster collaboration and exchange between stakeholders, and encourage innovative solutions to climate adaptation challenges. These objectives will be reviewed annually and monitored through a range of indicators.
- As such, the communication strategy identifies target groups and relevant communication channels and tools, utilising both digital and non-digital methods. The strategy includes an overview of how the website and social media accounts (Twitter and LinkedIn) will be used. It also discusses the implementation of other communication activities, such as workshops, external conferences, videos, a roadshow, and the Climate Adaptalabs, as these feed into the overall visibility of the project.
- The communication and dissemination strategy will be a living document, to be updated as the project progresses. It defines clear objectives and measurable indicators for success, which will be used to track impact and progress.

Figure 1: Diagram of communication, dissemination and exploitation overlap

1.1 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation

These three central interrelated activities pursue different goals, and all contribute to the overall recognition and uptakes of the project's activities and results. While these concepts are related, they serve different purposes and require different approaches. Their differences, purposes, and audiences, as well as specifics of their use in this strategy, are detailed below.

1.1.1 Communication

Communication refers to the process of exchanging information, ideas, or messages between individuals, groups, or organisations in a clear, effective, and timely manner. It aims to inform, promote, and share the actions, activities, and results of the project with targeted information and message to the different audiences. The aim is to engage in a two-way exchange with stakeholders, which can take various forms, including but not limited to verbal or written communication, visual communication, and digital communication.

Different tools will be exploited for this purpose. The detailed list of communication channels can be found in section 7 and the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) set out to achieve them can be found in section 9.3.

Communication goals

- Develop a visual identity that reflects the project's objectives and values to create a cohesive brand image (detailed in section 5)
- Determine the key communication channels that are most effective in reaching the target audiences and tailor the content for each channel (detailed in section 7)
- Identify and understand the target audiences to tailor the language, tone and style of the communication to resonate better with them (detailed in section 3)
- Determine the key messages that need to be communicated to ensure a clear and consistent message across all communication activities (detailed in section 3)
- Establish SMART objectives (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time manageable) to ensure the communication strategy is aligned with the overall goals of the project and track progress effectively (detailed in section 4)

1.1.2 Dissemination

Dissemination refers to the disclosure of the main results of the project. It is meant to make them known, accessible, and exploitable by any stakeholder that can learn, use or benefit from them; typically: the scientific community, policymakers, industry representatives, etc.

Dissemination is used to target researchers or academics, where researchers aim to share their findings with other researchers, practitioners, policymakers, or the general public, dissemination can take varied forms, including publications, presentations, workshops, and online platforms. In this case, they are targeted at a scientific audience as well as at policymakers.

Part of dissemination includes the production of various materials such as factsheets, policy briefs, and scientific publications to inform and engage with stakeholders. In addition, we will utilise direct engagement methods such as presenting the project at events like scientific conferences and webinars. Finally, we will also organise Climate Adaptalabs, adapted from the Hackathon method, to bring together stakeholders from various fields and facilitate transdisciplinary knowledge exchange. Through these activities, we aim to create a platform for effective communication and collaboration, enabling us to share our knowledge products and receive feedback from stakeholders. By sharing knowledge products, we hope to increase awareness of climate change and its impact, and ultimately, support stakeholders in implementing effective adaptation strategies.

Dissemination goals

- Provide accessible and user-friendly information and guidance on climate information and services to support end-users in their adaptation planning and action
- Enhance the quality, relevance and usefulness of near-term climate information and services for local to regional scales, particularly in relation to assessing risks due to extremes, climate impacts, and uncertainty
- Foster collaboration and exchange between researchers, practitioners and end-users, using transdisciplinary approaches to climate services and improve the overall value-chain of climate services
- Encourage grassroots insights, creative problem solving, and innovative solutions to climate adaptation challenges through the Climate Adaptalabs, providing a platform for collaboration and exchange between stakeholders

1.1.3 Exploitation

Finally, exploitation refers to the utilisation of the project results beyond the project's own activities for a specific purpose or practical use. It is often used in the context of innovation or entrepreneurship, with researchers or companies aiming to translate their research findings into commercial products, services, or technologies. It too can take various forms, such as patenting, licencing, or spin-off companies, but also policy proposals and recommendations. The concrete use made of the project's findings ensures the accessibility and exploitation of the project's data and results beyond its end, making sure that they can be used to contribute to special reports, policy proposals, etc.

Overall, the exploitation activities of I4C contribute to the legacy of the project and promote the wider use of its outcomes for the benefit of society.

A separate exploitation plan is being delivered at the end of April 2023. This plan should be the main reference for exploitation going forward. This document aims to provide only a short snapshot of exploitation in the context of other communication and dissemination activities.

Exploitation goals

- Leave a legacy of the project's outcomes and results
- Creation of an [EOSC open data space](#): The core products and tools developed by I4C will be made available in the EOSC open data space, facilitating seamless integration with other relevant datasets and software packages

- Creation of a climate hazard toolkit and adaptation support pack: able to be generalised into a roadmap for adaptation planning beyond the project's lifetime. These activities ensure that the science produced by I4C is available to stakeholder communities and beyond, particularly those involved in climate adaptation planning in urban areas

2. Overarching objectives

The strategy is focused on achieving both short and long-term objectives that are aligned with the project's overall goals.

In the short term, our objective is to create unique, coherent, and recognisable visual identities that will help us achieve our long-term objectives. Our long-term objectives are to *identify and reach the optimal audience, raise awareness about the vulnerability of cities to climate change, and the necessity to take action to improve resilience*. Additionally, we aim to promote the existence of climate data and its use to achieve sustainable change in climate action and policy. The objectives are detailed in a more in-depth manner below.

2.1 Short term objectives

Objective 1: Identify and reach the right audiences

The success of our project is dependent on identifying and reaching the right audiences. We aim to engage with a diverse range of stakeholders including policymakers, city officials, researchers, and the general public (citizens). In so doing, we can ensure that our messaging is received by those in the best position to make a positive impact on the environment through their action and/or their influence.

Objective 2: Creating a unique, coherent, and recognisable visual identity

To achieve our long-term objectives, we acknowledge the need for a unique, coherent, and recognisable visual identity. We have therefore created a visual identity that is visually appealing and memorable, as well as colour-blind proof.

Objective 3: Creating an editorial calendar for strategic web and social media dissemination

The editorial calendar will allow Arctik to plan and organise content for dissemination across various media channels, including the project's website and social media platforms. Its structure outlines the topics, formats, and distribution schedules for all communications, ensuring content is being delivered consistently, effectively, and in a timely fashion. A sample editorial calendar is provided in the Appendix. The

editorial calendar also provides a reference point to ensure that our messaging remains varied and that it evolves as the project evolves.

Objective 4: Bringing together key stakeholders at workshops and events (Climate Adaptalabs)

Bringing together stakeholders is a critical aspect of the I4C project as it allows for a continual process of iterative co-production across the Demonstrators. This process ensures that diverse actors, including physical and social scientists, consultants, municipal planners, NGOs, and other decision-makers, work together to solve pressing issues related to climate adaptation. By involving stakeholders, we can gain a better understanding of their concerns and priorities, leading to more targeted research and interventions.

One way we bring together actors is with (in person or online) events such as the Climate Adaptalabs . In addition, other outreach activities, such as a roadshow, attending and hosting external events will ensure that stakeholder engagement is prioritised.

2.2 Long-term objectives

Objective 1: Raise awareness about climate change in cities and the actions which can be taken to improve resilience (making I4C science actionable)

The impact of climate change on cities can be devastating if not adequately addressed. In line with the I4C approach to address and improve the full value chain of near-term predictions from global climate to local impacts, we aim to raise awareness about the vulnerability of cities to climate change and promote actions to improve resilience. With this awareness-raising campaign, we hope to encourage city officials and policymakers to take action to mitigate the impact of climate change in their regions/cities.

Objective 2: Promote the existence of climate data and how it can be used to achieve our goals

Through communication and dissemination we aim to promote the existence, usefulness and understanding of climate data in guiding policy and action. In so doing, we can ensure that our stakeholders have access to the necessary information to make informed decisions that will positively impact the environment.

Objective 3: Ensure a lasting impact of the research and results

Successful exploitation will have stakeholders invested in the tools and services of the project, as well as their maintenance and accessibility. By doing so, the project seeks

to ensure that its impact is lasting and that its research contributes to meaningful and lasting improvements in the quality, accessibility, and usability of climate information and services at local to regional scales.

3. Target audiences and messages

It is crucial for the success of I4C that the right audience is targeted with messages that resonate and inspire action. The target audiences and stakeholders likely to make a difference include policymakers, city planners, stakeholders, researchers, and the public. To best target these audiences, we will ask for consortium inputs to identifying the specific actors in each target audience and then crafting tailored messages to ensure that the project can effectively communicate its goals and build support for its mission.

A list of target audiences identified so far, as well as their messages and main mediums of communication, can be found below.

3.1 Main target audiences

I4C has the following target audience groups:

- Policymakers (city-level, regional-level, and EU level)
- Local, and regional organisations (ex. municipal actors, agencies, public health, and safety organisations)
- Academic and scientific community researchers active in climate science, civil society
- NGO's and youth groups
- Citizens/the general public

These actors are the ones who can directly share, use and implement the data, solutions, tools, and results created by the I4C project, so that they can be put to use in the different localities and have the impact they were designed to create. A dedicated Excel spreadsheet to track stakeholders for the project has been created and will continue to be updated throughout the project cycle. It has been added to the Annex for reference.

3.2 Sample messages per audience

Different messages will be delivered to the different targets, through the following communication channels.

Audience	A sample message / aim	Tools / channel
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cities in Europe face different climate challenges and scientists are working on understanding these better to create mitigation strategies - Understanding climate data is key to understanding climate change - Climate information is hard to understand – I4C is working on improving the understanding for citizens as well as scientists 	I4C Website Events (roadshow) Social media Videos Media (Press releases)
Academic, scientific, research and VIACS community (ex. Scientific research institutions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I4C gathers the expertise of climate, city and social experts to improve the quality and accessibility of climate information - Based on the case studies in the cities of Bergen, Paris, Barcelona and Prague, I4C will test its tailor-made solutions to their 4 distinct realities and challenges, so as to make the cities trailblazers and a model for future action elsewhere - I4C develops a scalable ready-to-use climate data space on the EOSC Space - I4C develops a climate hazards toolkit: a tool to improve risk assessments at the local scales and lend further support to adaptation planning 	I4C Website Newsletter Events (roadshow & Adaptalabs) Social media Press releases
Local, and regional organisations (ex. municipal actors, agencies, public health and safety organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding of how scientific knowledge can be converted into actionable information - What is climate data, how can you use it to use to mitigate the negative effects of climate change? - Inform on adaptation measures local actors can take against extreme weather events - Inform on the scalable ready-to-use climate data space developed by I4C on the EOSC Space. - Explain the climate hazards toolkit: a toolkit to improve risk assessments at the local scales and lend further support to adaptation planning 	I4C Website Newsletter Policy briefs Academic publications Events (roadshow) Social media
Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use outcomes of demonstrators to inform future policy decisions to ensure other cities can easily adapt to climate change events. - Highlight the pressing need to regulate activities that can directly or indirectly impact (positively or negatively) city resilience to climate change, justified by the varied and severe consequences of politics as usual 	Policy briefs I4C Website Newsletter Academic publications Media (Press releases) Events (Climate Adaptalabs)

<p>Civil society (NGO, youth groups, etc.)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide clear solutions in the form of the toolbox to support greater political efforts to accelerate societal transformation 	<p>Social media Events (Climate Adaptalabs) I4C Website Media (Press releases)</p>
--	---	---

4. Content strategy – Methodology

This section of the communication strategy depicts the method behind the use of the tools in our content strategy.

The methodology entails:

- raising awareness about the project and mobilising contacts over the course of the project (the marketing funnel – explained below)
- tailored messaging for the audiences
- aligning WP outputs with external communication
- multiplying messages beyond the I4C network (using multipliers and sister projects).

4.1 Raising awareness and ‘the Marketing Funnel’

In general, audiences need some time to warm up to a new project. It is rarely the case that someone who has a first interaction with a project or organisation immediately uses their recommendations or outputs. Often, such trust in and use of a project's outputs is established through repeated interactions with a project over time.

For this reason, all major communication actions will be structured around the marketing funnel principle. This funnel illustrates the journey an audience member takes from first hearing about I4C to *converting*, i.e., taking the desired action. It tries to have audience members move through the steps of *awareness*, *consideration*, and *decision to advocacy*:

- *awareness* – an audience member first encounters I4C on social media, during an event or in multiplier communication and takes a superficial interest
- *consideration* – an audience member has taken an interest in I4C and starts engaging more with its content and starts consuming more in-depth content. This can mean that they follow the project on social media, consume our editorial or video content or deliberately attend one of our events
- *decision* – an audience member starts using I4C outputs and recommendations
- *conversion/advocacy* – once an audience member converts (conversion), they become an advocate. In this role they can help boost or multiply our message or influence others.

It is important to raise awareness with and engage as many audience members as possible at the onset of the project, since a series of communication tools rely on stakeholders to create impact. These include:

- Events (Climate Adaptalabs, Roadshow, external events)
- Newsletters
- Social media

An audience does not move through the funnel as one block. At the starting point, different audience members are at different places in the funnel. Some of them are, for instance, already aware of the goals of I4C through previous interactions with the consortium partners' work and, therefore, prepared to consider or decide at an early stage. The conversion process will also have different speeds depending on an audience member's pre-existing issue involvement.

As such, we will make sure to balance content for audience members at all different stages of the funnel. On the one hand, this means providing more targeted content items to ensure that more mature audience members do not disengage. On the other hand, it is important to keep providing entry-level, bite-sized content to make sure new audience members can start moving through the funnel. If this does not happen, audience growth tapers off as the first segment(s) of the funnel empty out.

4.2 Engagement triangle

The strategic approach of the engagement triangle helps to structure communication activities over time. While the marketing funnel helps to structure who should be targeted by the content, the engagement triangle outlines which

types of content are needed for the different parts of the funnel.

The triangle has proven effective and facilitates placing different communication activities on a timeline following the different layers of the triangle leading to an effective engagement of target audiences, both internal and external. It

forms the basis for an effective process to secure target-oriented communication as well as for large-spectrum communication.

On top of the pyramid sits the campaign. A campaign serves to attract new audience members. Typically, a campaign will be organised twice a year, depending on the project outputs. The second level of the engagement triangle, top-topical communication, refers to engagements via external hooks such as a new climate policy or large event which creates a lot of buzz. On average, a top-topical communication action will be organised monthly or every two months.

To maintain a steady relationship over time, we will use a fixed format to enhance loyalty among audience members, which is to be done often and consistently. An example for such communication activities could be case study updates or news items. At the bottom of the pyramid, we find the flow. This refers to the daily interaction with audience members via social media and via email or through selected social media accounts.

5. Project branding

5.1 Visual identity and templates

Visual identity refers to the visual components that represent a project or organisation. This includes elements such as logos, colour schemes, typography, imagery, and other design elements that create a consistent and recognisable visual language. An attractive, coherent and recognisable visual identity adds value to branding and communication efforts, by providing a consistent and professional image to stakeholders and the public. It also helps to differentiate the project from other similar initiatives and creates a sense of unity and cohesion within the project team.

For the Impetus 4 Change project, a visual identity was developed that incorporates elements such as a logo, colour scheme as well as imagery consistent with the project's values and objectives. Applied across all communication materials, including websites, social media, and other project outputs, they create a coherent and recognisable visual language. To ensure project cohesion, templates were created based on the visual identity guidelines, including a deliverable template, a word template, a PowerPoint presentation template.

The full visual identity for Impetus 4 Change in the Appendix.

5.2 Flyer

Flyers are printed or online leaflets used to communicate key information about a project or initiative to a wider audience. Flyers are designed to highlight key messages and project objectives and can include eye-catching visuals to draw people's attention.

A dedicated I4C flyer will be created by month 12. It will be shared at events, and when reaching out to stakeholders to give them a general overview of the project. The flyer will be added to the project website and made available for print, when necessary, by project partners when they attend or host events. The flyer will be updated as the project evolves, to showcase results near the end of the project.

6. Tools and channels

6.1 Owned tools and channels

Owned tools and channels imply tools created and managed directly by the project such as the project website, social media, and newsletter. This opposes other channels such as the media.

6.1.1 Project website

The [Impetus4Change.eu](https://impetus4change.eu) website, already active, serves as the main reference point for the project, with a visually cohesive design and user-friendly interface that provides easy access to project updates and results for a diverse audience. It will serve as an essential resource for stakeholders at all levels and will provide a central location to access all project-related information.

Maintained and updated regularly, the website is directed toward the general public, ensuring that the project's goals and outcomes are easily comprehensible to all. The website is home to a range of content and communication materials, including core project information, details on the demonstrator cities, and information on the tools and solutions developed. It also provides news updates, event information, videos, press releases, and links to academic and scientific publications.

News pieces

The I4C website has a dedicated news section for updates about the project. Regular updates to be published on the website include updates on project activities, upcoming events, and new publications. These news items will be written as either feature articles, or short news briefs, depending on the nature of the announcement and the intended audience. All consortium members will be encouraged to draft news items and to share updates with the communication team. Once published, the news pieces will also be used as hook or angle for wider communication campaigns on social media to capture public attention and possibly even generate media coverage.

6.1.2 Social media

LinkedIn and Twitter were chosen as the main social media channels for I4C due to their effectiveness in reaching both the professional and scientific audience. LinkedIn is a platform widely used by professionals and organisations to share knowledge and expertise related to their respective fields, making it an ideal platform to share information on the project's activities and research. Twitter, on the other hand, is a highly interactive platform that can provide real-time updates on the project's

activities, as well as being an effective tool for networking and engaging with stakeholders. The hashtag #I4C will be used for all posts to ensure consistency in branding and awareness throughout the project.

Twitter

A [Twitter account](#) has already been created for the project. For Twitter, the content will focus on short, concise messages that can be easily shared and retweeted. The goal is to provide updates on the project's progress, highlight new publications and events, and engage with stakeholders and the broader community especially during events. The tweets will include relevant hashtags and mentions to reach a wider audience and increase visibility. This platform is ideal for engaging with policymakers, government agencies, and adaptation science communities, as well as the general public interested in climate change and climate services.

LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn account](#) has already been created for the project. The content for LinkedIn will be more in-depth, focusing on longer-form articles and updates that highlight the project's achievements and impact. The content will be tailored to a more professional audience, including researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. LinkedIn will also be used to share project updates and publications, as well as job postings and opportunities for collaboration. The platform is ideal for building a professional network, connecting with potential partners and collaborators, and establishing the project as a thought leader in the field of climate services.

Communication campaigns

Throughout the project, we will structure communication campaigns around the project results. These campaigns will be a series of posts on a related topic with the addition of eye-catching visuals or videos. Working closely with WP leaders as results are developing is key to this.

Local-level campaign

In addition, I4C will run a local-level-specific communication campaign to raise awareness and build support for the project's goals at the local level of the Demonstrators. This type of campaign involves targeted communication efforts aimed at specific local communities and can be an effective way to engage with both stakeholders and citizens. Content used for this purpose would include social media posts, press releases, guest articles, or interviews highlighting the project's benefits and encouraging community involvement. The messages will be translated to ensure maximum accessibility.

The use of a local-level communication campaign can also help to foster community ownership and engagement in I4C. By involving local stakeholders and providing them with the tools and information they need to act, the campaign can help to build a sense of collective responsibility for addressing the challenges of climate change. Moreover, the campaign can help to identify and address community-specific barriers to climate action, such as lack of resources or cultural barriers.

Given the identification and definition of a target audience, the campaign would concretely aim to leverage local media, foster collaboration with local partners, and create opportunities for in-person engagement. Collaboration with local partners such as NGOs, community organisations, or businesses can also help reaching out to the target audience more effectively.

6.1.3 Newsletter

Newsletters are an effective way to keep stakeholders informed and engaged with project developments. Distributed every six months, the purpose of the newsletter is to share progress updates, upcoming events, and relevant information related to the project. The newsletter will also include highlights of our engagement with stakeholders, such as results from surveys and feedback received from Climate Adaptalabs. We will also utilise the newsletter to showcase any new products or tools that have been developed and to share scientific publications resulting from the project.

The target audience for the newsletter includes stakeholders at the local, regional, national and EU levels, policymakers, the scientific community, and journalists. To maximise outreach, we will also target other project newsletters with a similar focus and audience to ours (multipliers – see also section 7.2). This cross-promotion will help to expand our reach and ensure that our stakeholders are kept up to date with our progress. Additionally, we will encourage feedback and suggestions from our newsletter subscribers to help us continually improve our communication strategy and ensure that the newsletter meets their needs. Our aim is to have more than 100 subscribed to the newsletter by the end of the project.

7. Making I4C actionable – Dissemination and engagement

7.1 Promoting accessibility

Key to making I4C actionable is ensuring accessibility and ease of understanding of the project outputs. This section focuses on the videos which will be produced as well as the dissemination activities foreseen for the project.

7.1.1 Videos

Throughout the project, a total of 15 videos will be created, of which 10 will be video blogs by researchers. In addition, two animated video explainer videos will be created for public consumption to ensure accessibility of the key science concepts of the project. The video topics foreseen are below as well as the estimated timeline and audience.

Video topic	Audience	Timeline
Project introduction animation video	All audiences	Dissemination by M10
Video blog (10): short video content of project overview, progress, research, results	Academic	Preparation M16-24, Dissemination M18-M28 (depending on results)
Explainer video: Why is near-term climate important? (Animation video)	Academic audiences, policymakers	Dissemination by M18
Explainer video: what is super modelling (Animation video)	Academic audiences	Dissemination by M24
Global modellers	Academic audiences	Dissemination by M25
Adaptalabs final video	All audiences (but focus on youth and academic)	Dissemination by M48

7.2 Multipliers

Multipliers are key to ensuring a quick uptake of project outputs with relevant audiences within a short amount of time. Multipliers are related projects or initiatives which can be used to 'multiply' or share I4C's messages. To be useful they need to have an established network of contacts or subscribers who would be innately

interested in I4C. To use these multipliers, we will establish contact with them and ask them in what way we can collaborate to ensure that it is mutually beneficial. For instance, they could participate in a project event, or we could co-write an article or press release with them.

7.2.1 Mapping multipliers and newsletters

Before M12, the project will conduct a mapping exercise to identify relevant multipliers and newsletters that focus on climate change adaptation and mitigation. The newsletters will be mapped based on factors such as audience, frequency of publication, and topic areas covered. Then we will engage with the newsletter editors and authors to establish partnerships and explore opportunities to disseminate information about the project's research and activities.

7.2.2 Toolkit

I4C will prepare a toolkit by M12 that can be easily utilised by project partners and multipliers to broaden the reach of the project and create more impact. The toolkit will contain a package of communication materials that can be easily copied and pasted for use on social media or on a website, including:

- a one-page description
- a flyer
- ready-made Social Media posts (for LinkedIn and Twitter)
- banners for web
- the general I4C video

These materials will be designed to ensure with accessibility in mind, aiming for them to be easily shareable to promote the project and its key messages. The target audience for the toolkit includes stakeholders at local, regional, national, and EU levels, policymakers, the scientific community, scientific communication community, and journalists.

7.2.3 Media engagement

In the coming months, we will map a list of key media outlets which are relevant to the project. Over the course of the project, we will reach out to journalists at these outlets with up to 10 press releases. Engagement with the media will be strategic and timely to garner as much attention and impact as possible. Therefore, reach out will only occur when we have key messages which are deemed 'newsworthy'.

7.3 Dissemination

7.2.1 Policy briefs

The project will produce policy briefs in M24 and M45 to provide concise and informative overviews of research findings and recommendations for policymakers, government agencies, EU agencies, and the adaptation science community. The policy briefs will be produced with a focus on clarity and concision, using accessible language and incorporating relevant graphics and visuals. These briefs will be an essential tool for the project in disseminating information to policymakers. The policy briefs will be made available online and presented at ECCA/COP town halls and EU Science2Policy events. Through this approach, the policy briefs will enable the project to engage with stakeholders and ensure the dissemination of the project's findings and recommendations to policymakers and other relevant audiences, thereby contributing to informed decision-making and the adoption of climate adaptation measures.

5.2.5 Scientific publications and Zenodo

All project partners will be asked to share publications with the communication team for further dissemination on social media and in newsletters. These publications will also be added to the dedicated [Zenodo page](#) linked on the website Library section.

8. Events

8.1 Climate Adaptalabs

Figure 2: I4C Climate Adaptalab logo

The purpose of the I4C Adaptalabs is to bring together a diverse group of actors, including physical and social scientists, consultants, municipal planners, NGOs, and others from across disciplines and sectors to collaborate on pressing issues related to the project.

Inspired by the Hackathon format, the Adaptalabs will have participants work together intensively over 2 days on solutions to a given challenge. The challenges will be based on issues and goals related to I4C and will therefore focus on climate adaptation and services. The focus is on group work, so that participants have time

to get to know one another, share ideas and develop solutions while also promoting trust-building and open dialogue. The audience will initially be stakeholders and researchers involved in I4C, but we will likely open participation to others working in the climate service arena. Sharing knowledge and ideas within I4C consortium is important, but we must work together with others to ensure a long-lasting and wide impact.

The first Adaptalab is planned to take place in Paris in November or December 2023. We hope to gather 60-80 people who will be divided into 10-12 working groups. The event will begin with a few short inspirational presentations and information. Then the groups will work together on the challenge. The challenge for the first Adaptalab will focus on making mock-ups for the climate service that I4C will develop. Groups will discuss what type of information is needed, where this information will be accessed, how it can be accessed and how it can be integrated into real-life decision-making processes. The groups will make posters to display their work process and solutions. The event will conclude with a poster session where all participants (and potentially other invitees) can circulate and discuss all the solutions that the groups have developed.

Critical in inspiring climate action and improving decision-making, as they involve current and future decision-makers in the scientific process, these events will also create buzz about the project through social media, promoting awareness of the project's objectives and outcomes.

8.2 Roadshow

The roadshow for the project would consist in a series of events held in various locations, including public meetings, workshops, and presentations. Its primary objective would be to disseminate and communicate information about the I4C to the general public and policymakers. By generating a buzz around the project's research outcomes, the events would be used to showcase the outputs from the project, piggybacking off larger conference or event to ensure a high level of attendance and visibility. The roadshow events would also provide the project team with the chance to collect feedback from local stakeholders, build links with other local initiatives and projects, and gather data that would help shape the project's activities and research.

The roadshow materials may include a booth, flyer, and roll-up, among others, making it easy for attendees to access information about the project and take it away with them. We aim to create this roadshow in the most sustainable way possible, using screens where possible instead of printed roll-ups.

8.3 External events

Tracking and mapping external events will play an important role in the overall communication strategy of the I4C project. It will help the project team to identify

and attend key events that are relevant to their research and objectives and for them to present their work and engage with stakeholders, policymakers, and experts. The project has a goal of 30 conference presentations over the project lifecycle.

8.3.1 Mapping external events

Mapping the upcoming external events will also help the team to plan their schedule and allocate resources effectively. A dedicated event mapping will be done by M12 and updated throughout the project. We foresee events such as the EU Science2Policy event, ECCA/COP town halls, and EGU, as highly relevant to the project's research and objectives. Attending these events can increase the visibility of the project and create opportunities for collaboration and partnership. Overall, tracking the outcome of these events will be crucial for the project's success in achieving its communication and dissemination goals.

9. Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation are activities which track the overall progress and impact of the communication and dissemination activities. To ensure that the communication team has all the information they need to communicate about the project, an internal communication meeting will be held every two months including partners from WP7 and external partners as needed. In addition, a communication tracker has been put in place and KPIs have been estimated based on previous projects for use throughout the project and especially during yearly evaluations.

9.1 Bi-monthly internal communication

Bi-monthly (every two months) meetings with the WP7 partners and other WP leads will ensure effective communication and collaboration among all partners involved in the implementation of the I4C project. These meetings will provide a platform for partners to share updates, discuss progress and address any challenges that may arise. Regular communication through meetings or email exchanges ensures that all partners are informed about the latest developments and have a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities. This allows for timely decision-making and swift resolution of issues that may impact the project's success.

9.2 Communication/dissemination tracker

A dedicated Excel document (in Annex) has been made available for all partners to use to track their activities. The tracker includes a section for event attendance, publications, event hosting and more. It will be referenced at

9.3 Communication KPIs

Communication goals such as KPIs are key to ensuring the project is reaching the level of impact. We will refer to these goals yearly to track how social media

campaigns, and event engagement are progressing and adapt our methods if they are in line with the goals.

	Audience goal	Frequency (avg)	Metrics
Twitter	400 followers	8 posts per month	Engagement Followers: >2000 Website visits Video views
LinkedIn	150 followers	4 post per month	Engagement Website visits Video views
Newsletter	100 subscribers	Twice yearly	Number of link click Number of subscribers: >100
Event engagement	Engage with 500+ participants	3 Climate Adaptalabs	Number of participants: 50/event

9.3 Challenges and opportunities

Challenge: Communication about complex topics to a heterogenous audience

Solution:

- Use simple and straightforward language.
- Describe the project with a story: use concrete examples and socio-economic impacts.
- Adapt the message to the target audience.

Challenge: Communication can be left aside or forgotten about internally

Solution:

- There will be a standing mention in the internal newsletter to remind consortium member to communicate about their work to Arctik.
- The focus will be kept on communication activities relevant to deliverables.
- Arctik will ensure consortium members have all the tools they need to communicate through toolkits and internal training.
- Reminders will be sent to consortium member to urge their contribution.
- Joining WP meetings when relevant to gather information.

9.4 List of deliverables

	Deliverable	Deadline
D 7.1	Communication and dissemination strategy	M 6 (ARCTIK)
D7.2	Interim report on communication and dissemination activities inc. Climate Adaptalabs Task 7.1,7.2,7.3	M 24 (ARCTIK)
D7.3	Final report on communication and dissemination activities inc. Climate Adaptalabs, Task 7.1, 7.2, 7.3	M 47 (ARCTIK)
D 7.4	Exploitation plan	M 6 (NORCE)
D7.5	Interim report on exploitation activities	M 24 (CSIC)
D7.6	Final report on exploitation activities	M 47 (CSIC)

10. Appendix

Impetus 4 Change

Brand guidelines

CONCEPT

Impetus:

- The force or energy with which a body moves.
- Something that makes a process or activity happen or happen more quickly.
- Impulsion, energy, force, power, push.

(Origine: Oxford Languages)

LOGOS

IMPETUS
4 CHANGE
T U H A N U E

I4C
T U E

COLORS

RGB 30 36 83, **CMYK** 100 95 37 33

RGB
103 178 231
CMYK
55 16 0 0

RGB
109 205 177
CMYK
54 0 39 0

RGB
243 236 122
CMYK
0 0 58 0

RGB 255 86 48, **CMYK** 0 80 85 0

TYPOGRAPHY

Barlow Condensed, bold

Barlow, regular italic

Barlow, regular

Main title

Subtitle, introduction, tagline, etc...
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet

Body. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

Body. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

STAKEHOLDERS (in field of project)						
name	type	what they are	country	website	Twitter	
EU Climate Action	DG CLIMA		europa		@EUClimateAction @EUScienceInnov, @PaolaLeporiEU	
EU Science and Innovation United Nation Climate Change			europa worldwide		@UNFCCC	
International Science Council	climate information	The global voice for science. Through our members, partners and associates, we aim to advance science as a global public good.			@ISC	
Iconics	climate information	organizes the process of developing new socioeconomic scenarios to facilitate interdisciplinary research and assessment on climate change			@iconics_ssp	
EOSC	climate information	European open science cloud			@eosassociation	
National Centers for Environmental Information (National Oceanic and atmospheric administration)	climate information	The leading american authority for environmental data, and manage one of the largest archives of atmospheric, coastal, geophysical, and oceanic research in the world.	USA	https://www.noaa.gov	@NOAAANCEI	
Sandbag	climate information	Think tank using data analysis to build evidence-based campaigns on climate policy.			@sandbag_eu	
CDP (Disclosure Impact Action)	environmental impact information	CDP is a not-for-profit charity that runs the global disclosure system for investors, companies, cities, states and regions to manage their environmental impacts.	worldwide	https://www.cdp.com	@CDP	
Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)	climate change assessment	UN body for assessing to science related to climate change			@IPCC_CH	
European Met Society	meteorological information	The association of meteorological societies in Europe			@EuropeanMetSoc	
World Meteorological Organization	meteorological information				@WMO	
	city of Bergen stakeholder				@MParisCentre Paris @parisjecoute @paris2024	
	city of Paris stakeholder					
	city of Barcelona stakeholder					
	city of Prague stakeholder					
EU Research	climate research institute / research center	EU Research provides a link between pioneering research and thought leaders in global #academia, #business and #government.	europa		@EU_RESEARCH	
Terri	climate research institute / research center	independent not-for-profit research institute focused on energy, environment, and sustainable development.			@teriin	
IVM	climate research institute / research center	Leading in Sustainability Science: Institute for Environmental Studies in @VU_Science at @VUamsterdam			@VU_IVM @raedhamed1, @s_nirandjan	
UK Universities Climate Network	climate research institute / research center	group of 80+ UK universities and research centres working together for a zero carbon, resilient future.	UK		@UKClimateUnis	
Social Science research council (SSRC)	Social science research institute / research center				@ssrc_org	
Stanford - Institute for research in the social sciences	Social science research institute / research center		USA	https://iris.stanford.edu	@StanfordIRISS	
receipt	EU funded project in climate initiatives		europa		@RECEIPT_eu	
EIT Climate-KIC	EU funded project in climate initiatives	Europe's leading climate innovation initiative	europa		@ClimateKIC	
ARSINOE	EU funded project in climate initiatives	Climate-resilient regions through systemic solutions and innovations	europa		@ARSINOE_EU	
Myriad	EU funded project in climate initiatives		europa		@Myriad_EU	
PolarRES	EU funded project in climate initiatives	Exploring the future climates of the Polar regions	europa		@PolarRES_eu	
ISC	EU funded project in climate initiatives		europa		@ISC	
GoNEXUS	EU funded project in climate initiatives		europa		@GoNEXUSProject	
AfriAlliance	EU funded project in climate initiatives	Innovation Alliance for Water & Climate. Supporting knowledge sharing & tech transfer within Africa & between Africa-EU	europa		@AfriAlliance1	
Connecting health and climate change	EU funded project in climate initiatives	Bringing together leaders in #climatechange & #health research & coordinating a network of climate & health projects http://enbel-project.eu .	europa		@ENBEL_H2020	
Climate Change Committee		The Climate Change Committee (CCC) is an independent, statutory body established under the Climate Change Act 2008. Our purpose is to advise the UK and devolved governments on emissions targets and to report to Parliament on progress made in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and preparing for and adapting to the impacts of climate change.	UK	https://www.ccc.org.uk	@theCCCuk	
Suggested by I4C members						
C40	related organisation					
URBACT	related organisation					
World Bank	related organisation	(policy and climate related strategies)				
Project NextGems					@nextgems_eu	
FPS URB-RCC						
EC Horizon Europe Project FOCI						
EUCP						
climateurope						
climateurope2						
contacts from Receipt climate story line (https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/u6t9qeu6k4s3kbio1tyok/Arctic-CFC-Joint-policy-Brief-dissemination.xlsx?cloud_editor=excel&dl=0)						
European Climate Foundation						